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NORMS AND PROFESSIONAL CULTURE IN FRONTLINE EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT**

Abstract [It]: La tesi principale è che la legalità della governance delle emergenze dipende dalla cultura professionale dei funzionari di prossimità più che dal disegno costituzionale. Distingue uno stato di emergenza ancorato al diritto da uno stato di eccezione extra-legale e mostra perché la prassi sfugge al pieno controllo testuale. Evidenzia poi che norme indeterminate, complessità situazionale, urgenza e l'autonomia dei funzionari rendono necessaria la discrezionalità, ma incline all'arbitrio. La cultura professionale media questo spazio—ideali autoritari e democratici corrispondono a pratiche che erodono o preservano la legalità—spostando le prescrizioni verso formazione, accountability e leadership.

Abstract [En]: The paper's main claim is that the legality of emergency governance hinges on frontline professional culture more than constitutional design. It distinguishes a law-embedded state of emergency from an extra-legal state of exception and then shows why practice escapes full textual control. It then shows that underdeterminate norms, situational complexity, urgency, and street-level autonomy make discretion necessary yet prone to arbitrariness. Professional culture mediates this space—the “authoritarian vs democratic” ideals map to “legality-eroding vs legality-preserving” practices—shifting prescriptions toward training, accountability, and leadership.

Parole chiave: Emergenza, Cultura professionale, Discrezionalità, Stato di emergenza, Funzionari di prossimità.

Keywords: Emergency, Professional Culture, Discretionality, State of Emergency, Frontline Agents

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1. Introduction

Imagine the following scenario: an unprecedented heatwave hits a large metropolitan region and meteorological forecasts predict that temperatures will remain critically high for several weeks. The region experiences a surge of heat-related illnesses and deaths, with hospitals reporting overcrowding. Power outages affect wide residential areas so that necessary cooling is scarcely available to those in need. In response, the national government declares a constitutional state of emergency, thus activating a normative framework designed to provide temporary extraordinary powers needed to efficiently address the crisis situation.

Acting on this constitutional authorization, the central emergency authority issues a decree instructing local emergency services to ensure that at-risk individuals remain indoors during peak heat hours and, if necessary, are relocated to designated cooling facilities. The decree states that fundamental rights remain in force and instructs emergency officials to rely on persuasion rather than coercion whenever possible. However, while the decree provides a standardized action plan, as the heatwave persists, emergency response unfolds very differently across communities.

In one part of the region, local emergency personnel focus on disseminating information, assisting voluntary relocation, and intervening coercively only in extreme cases where individuals' lives seem to be in immediate danger. Officers document each intervention and consult supervisors when uncertainties arise. In general, they perceive their emergency powers as strictly legally contained. In another part of the region, however, frontline emergency agents adopt a markedly different approach. Interpreting the same decree as a mandate to do whatever is necessary, they begin conducting door-to-door checks, ordering residents to remain indoors, and threatening fines or detention for non-compliance. In some cases, they even forcibly relocate individuals without personalized assessment, written records, or opportunity to appeal the decision.

From a purely formal perspective, both groups of agents operate under the same emergency law. Yet, the nature of frontline actions tells two radically different stories as the discretionary space that necessarily opens up at the frontlines is used in two significantly different ways. If emergency powers are constitutionally constrained and normatively regulated, what actually explains the possibility of such divergent exercise of the same emergency powers at the frontlines? What mediates between constitutionally framed emergency powers and their concrete exercise in frontline practice?

2. The frontline perspective: a theoretical blind spot

In this article, I defend the following descriptive claim: the reality of emergency management is not primarily determined by theoretical models or normative texts, but by how frontline emergency agents (such as firefighters, police officers, civil protection agents,

medical personnel etc.) perceive their own roles and the value of legality under conditions of stress. More specifically, I argue that differences in the exercise of emergency powers, even when falling within the same theoretical model or normative framework, are crucially determined by ‘the professional (legal) culture’ of frontline emergency agents.

In so arguing, I take my cue from Carl Friedrich who, in his seminal *Constitutional Government and Democracy*, poignantly observed that

«there are no ultimate institutional safeguards available for insuring that emergency powers be used for the purpose of preserving the constitution. Only the people’s own determination to see them so used can make sure of that, provided the constitution has placed the limitations upon the exercise of dictatorial powers»¹.

Friedrich’s observations are illuminating for at least two reasons. Firstly, because he reminds us that the efficacy of abstract legal instruments is contingent upon the actions of human agents. That is, he argues that normative documents and institutional set-ups are not self-executing but rather require implementation by flesh-and-blood individuals. Secondly, because he emphasizes that, regardless of this fact, abstract models and normative instruments are not at all irrelevant but, rather, that they play a crucial role in delineating in advance the sphere of legally permissible behaviour.

As to the first point, a closer look at the academic production on the topics of this article reveals that the bulk of contemporary legal-theoretical and constitutionalist literature deals precisely with those theoretical models and normative frameworks of emergency management (I will call this “the design level” of emergency management)². On the other hand, what goes on at the level of emergency organizations, and the individuals who deal with emergencies operationally (i.e. “the frontline level” of emergency management), has been grossly overlooked by mainstream legal scholarship³. How can this oversight of

¹ C. FRIEDRICH, *Constitutional Government and Democracy: Theory and Practice in Europe and America*, Boston, Little, Brown and Company, 1941, 247.

² See, for instance, G. AGAMBEN, *Stato di eccezione*, Torino, Bollati Boringhieri, 2003; G. MARAZZITA, *L'emergenza costituzionale. Definizioni e modelli*, Milano, Giuffrè, 2003; E. POSNER – A. VERMEULE, *Accommodating Emergencies*, in *Stanford Law Review*, n. 56/2003; B. ACKERMAN, *The Emergency Constitution*, in *The Yale Law Journal*, n. 113(5)/2004; J. FERREJOHN – P. PASQUINO, *The law of the exception: A typology of emergency powers*, in *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, n. 2(2)/2004; K.L. SCHEPPELE, *Law in a Time of Emergency: States of Exception and the Temptations of 9/11*, in *University of Pennsylvania Journal of Constitutional Law*, n. 6(5)/2004; O. GROSS – F. NÍ AOLÁIN, *Law in Times of Crisis. Emergency Powers in Theory and Practice*, New York, Cambridge University Press, 2006; D. DYZENHAUS, *The Constitution of Law. Legality in a Time of Emergency*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2006; N. LAZAR, *States of Emergency in Liberal Democracy*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2009; C. FATOVIC, *Outside the Law. Emergency and Executive Power*, Baltimore, The Johns Hopkins University Press, 2009; G. TUSSEAU, *The Concept of Constitutional Emergency Power: A Theoretical and Comparative Approach*, in *ARSP: Archiv für Rechts- und Sozialphilosophie / Archives for Philosophy of Law and Social Philosophy*, n. 97(4)/2011; A. GREENE, *Permanent States of Emergency and the Rule of Law: Constitutions in an Age of Crisis*, Oxford, Hart Publishing, 2018; R. ALBERT – Y. ROZNAI (a cura di), *Constitutionalism Under Extreme Conditions. Law, Emergency, Exception*, Cham, Springer, 2020; L. BISHAI (a cura di), *Law, Security and the State of Perpetual Emergency*, Cham, Springer, 2020; G. SERGES, *La dimensione costituzionale dell'urgenza. Studio su di una nozione*, Napoli, Editoriale Scientifica, 2020; M. CROCE – A. SALVATORE, *Cos'è lo stato di eccezione*, Milano, Nottetempo, 2022; M. Belov (a cura di), *Constitutional Polycrisis and Emergency Constitutionalism*, Cham, Springer, 2025; G.-G. FUSCO – P. TACIK, *Law and the Exception. Towards a New Paradigm*, Abingdon, Routledge, 2026.

³ I do not address mid-level emergency management in this article. On the one hand, because it only partially overlaps with the strategic or managerial level discussed earlier. Core normative and strategic decisions are made at

frontline emergency management in the pertinent literature be explained? This omission, it seems, echoes Clinton Rossiter's statement, from his influential *Constitutional Dictatorship*, that «[c]risis government is primarily and often exclusively the business of presidents and prime ministers»⁴. Rossiter, then, appears to argue that all relevant activities in emergency management occur at the design level – and so it is at this level that jurists and constitutional lawyers should do their work.

On my view, while abstractions and generalizations do lie at the heart of a legal philosophers' work, the disregard for how the abstract models and general norms are actually implemented is nevertheless striking. This is especially so considering that emergencies are by nature frontline phenomena that produce their effects in the actual (i.e. physical) environment and require direct action to suppress them. Thus, as Friedrich reminds us, regardless of the fact that the role of theoretical models and constitutional frameworks is highly relevant, it is ultimately not these ideal-types and abstract institutions that do the actual emergency work, but rather flesh-and-blood individuals at the emergency frontlines. The actual site of (emergency) legality is, therefore, to be found in the actions of frontline emergency agents. Our analytical work should reflect this reality. Therefore, in this article, I seek to draw attention to this underexamined aspect of emergency management, particularly obscured in jurisprudential literature, and demonstrate its theoretical relevance.

As to the second point, the shift in focus to the frontlines proposed herein should, in fact, not be understood as a posture that theoretical models and normative frameworks are somehow irrelevant or useless. To the contrary, they perform an indispensable function – in general and for the analysis undertaken here. First, because they constitute the 'conceptual and normative background' within which frontline emergency agents develop their professional self-understanding and operational practices. In this sense, these models and frameworks structure what counts as legally relevant and morally justified reasons for action of frontline agents. Second, because they provide 'the evaluative yardstick' by which the legality of frontline action can be assessed. The ability to distinguish legal from illegal action presupposes normative standards against which such actions can concretely be evaluated. Crucially, these standards are internal to the legal order itself and are indispensable for any critical account of emergency governance.

Thus, while in this article I focus on analysing the nature of frontline activities in emergency management, I do not obscure the design level of analysis. In fact, I begin (3.) by sketching out a conceptual distinction between two abstract emergency response models. I call "the state of emergency" the model that grounds action in legally regulated norms and procedures, while I call "the state of exception" the *de facto* condition of extra-

design level, while mid-level management is largely limited to refining and implementing these decisions without engaging with major constitutional issues. From a frontline perspective, on the other hand, mid-level agents are also of limited relevance, as their work is conducted at a distance, away from the immediate hierarchical pressures and conditions faced by frontline emergency responders.

⁴ C. ROSSITER, *Constitutional Dictatorship. Crisis Government in the Modern Democracies*, Princeton, Princeton University Press, 1948, 12 (italics in the original).

legal responses to emergencies. Thereafter (4.), I examine the structural characteristics of frontline emergency decision-making, focusing on the inherent discretion that frontline agents possess, and on how this discretion incorporates the risk of degenerating into extra-legal arbitrariness. In the next section (5.), I argue that slippage into extra-legality is not necessary and that the nature of emergency responses ultimately depends on the legal culture instilled (through training and other forms of professional socialization) in the agents responsible for tackling emergencies on the frontlines. Finally (6.), I draw some conclusions.

3. The design level: emergencies, and “the state of emergency” vs “state of exception” framework

At this point, it is necessary to clarify the conceptual framework within which frontline emergency governance will be analyzed. Here, I provide but a sketchy definition of the phenomena forming this structure.

First of all, I define “emergencies” as temporary extraordinary events of particular intensity that are perceived as posing a serious threat to important (legally protected) goods, values, principles or interests of a given political community, so that extraordinary measures are deemed necessary to stop or counter them, and to ensure as quick as possible return to social and political normality (*status quo ante*)⁵. Whether natural (e.g. earthquakes, floods, pandemics etc.), political (e.g. terrorist attacks) or economic (e.g. extreme inflation) in origin⁶, emergencies are characterized by urgency⁷, importance, and perceived insufficiency of ordinary governance mechanisms.

The central dilemma in this regard concerns ‘the character’ of the response to emergencies. Do reactions to emergencies remain embedded within the legal order – albeit in modified forms – or do they require a suspension of ordinary legality to be efficient?⁸ In simpler terms, should the response to emergencies be legal or extra-legal? I suggest that this dilemma can be articulated as the distinction between the “state of emergency” and the “state of exception” models of emergency management.

⁵ This definition actually already presupposes the rejection of the so-called Business-as-Usual model of emergency management, according to which ‘ordinary’ law already provides all the resources required to successfully fend off an emergency. Thus, on this approach, there is no need to suspend, modify, or re-interpret ordinary law. Cf. O. GROSS – F. NÍ AOLÁIN, *Law in Times of Crisis. Emergency Powers in Theory and Practice*, cit., 87-88.

⁶ Cf. G. TUSSEAU, *The Concept of Constitutional Emergency Power: A Theoretical and Comparative Approach*, cit., 520 f. (quoting G. MARAZZITA, *L'emergenza costituzionale. Definizioni e modelli*, cit., 162-163). See also Piergigli, who distinguishes between political (for example, insurrections, economic crises, ecological disasters etc.) and technical (natural disasters, epidemics etc.) emergencies. The main point of distinction is, according to this author, the fact that political emergencies derive from man's activity and directly challenge the established order and institutional continuity, whereas technical emergencies are determined by natural events and therefore politically neutral, posing problems such as protecting the safety of the population. V. PIERGIGLI, *Potere e stato di emergenza*, in *Enciclopedia del diritto* (V). *Potere e costituzione*, Milano, Giuffrè, 2023, 602.

⁷ Cf. G. SERGES, *La dimensione costituzionale dell'urgenza. Studio su di una nozione*, cit.

⁸ Cf. M. CROCE – A. SALVATORE, *Cos'è lo stato di eccezione*, cit., 35.

I propose to redefine⁹ “the state of emergency” as a response to an emergency that (i) is law-based; (ii) involves structural modifications to the constitutional architecture; (iii) follows a reasoned decision of an (authorized) agent concerning the necessity of such a response; and (iv) pursues the purpose of restoring the social and political normality. On the contrary, I propose to redefine “the state of exception” as a response to an emergency that (i) is extra-legal; (ii) involves structural modifications of the constitutional architecture; (iii) follows an arbitrary decision of an (unauthorized) agent about the necessity of such a response; and (iv) pursues the purpose of either restoring the social and political normality or modifying some aspect thereof.

Already a quick comparison of the two redefinitions allows us to gather that the distinction between the state of emergency and the state of exception fundamentally turns on two criteria: (1) the normative status of the response (legal *vs* extra-legal); and (2) the authority and character of decision-making (legally authorized and reasoned *vs* legally unauthorized and arbitrary)¹⁰.

⁹ The task of defining a particular term can be undertaken in several ways. Firstly, one can provide a “lexical definition” to describe the way in which the defined term is commonly used within a particular social group; secondly, a definition can prescribe a particular use of the defined term (a “stipulative definition”); finally, a definition can either specify or modify the meaning of the defined term. Such a combination of the two aforementioned types of definitions is called a “re-definition”. Herein, I adopt this approach. In so doing, I follow U. SCARPELLI, *La definizione nel diritto* (1959), in U. SCARPELLI – P. DI LUCIA, *Il linguaggio del diritto*, Bologna, LED Edizioni Universitarie, 1994 and, through him, R. ROBINSON, *Definition*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1954.

¹⁰ (1) As to the question of ‘structural modifications’ of the constitutional architecture, emergency-related norms typically allow for the following kinds of changes: (a) changes in power dynamics between different branches of government (e.g. transferring the major decision-making powers from the legislator to the executive); (b) alterations to the decision-making acts and procedures (e.g. a shift from statutes to executive acts as the primary decision-making instruments, as well as their adoption according to simplified procedures); and, most importantly, (c) attribution of extraordinary powers to the empowered agent (primarily, the ability to temporarily derogate certain constitutional rights) – see G. TUSSEAU, *The Concept of Constitutional Emergency Power*, cit., 503 ss. Of course, on the extra-legal approach of the state of exception, seeing how formal declaration is lacking, the nature and success of structural modifications will hinge on the acting agent’s capacity to convince the target audience of their necessity. On this point, I follow the securitization blueprint as presented by the Copenhagen school of security studies (see B. BUZAN – O. WAEVER – J. DE WILDE, *Security: A New Framework for Analysis*, Boulder/London, Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1998). We should note that the possibilities of such a move succeeding are not marginal, as it is well-known that emergencies have a “consensus-building” capacity, meaning that they usually succeed in unifying the opinions of political adversaries as to what is to be done to eliminate the threat. This is what is usually called the “rally ‘round the flag’” effect. On this, see, for instance, O. GROSS – F. NÍ AOLÁIN, *Law in Times of Crisis. Emergency Powers in Theory and Practice*, cit., 64.

(2) As to the question of the ‘purpose’ of the state of emergency or the state of exception, I claim it is to enable the authorized agent to confront the emergency efficaciously and, thus, to stop or counter it, and then to return as quickly as possible to the social and political normality. I take such a ‘conservative-restorative purpose’ to be an essential element of the state of emergency. Clinton Rossiter is particularly clear on this point. He argues that the extraordinary government established in times of emergency, «can have no other purposes than the preservation of the independence of the state, the maintenance of the existing constitutional order, and the defence of the political and social liberties of the people» – or, to put it simply, «the complete restoration of the *status quo ante bellum*» (C. ROSSITER, *Constitutional Dictatorship. Crisis Government in the Modern Democracies*, cit., 7). See also C. FRIEDRICH, *Constitutional Government and Democracy: Theory and Practice in Europe and America*, cit., 246. On the other hand, while the purpose of the extra-legal approach may be to modify some aspect of the constitutional architecture or even overturn the constituted order (an ‘evolutive-revolutionary purpose’), this option nevertheless seems quite distant, at least in today’s relatively stable constitutional democracies (illiberal regimes, be they ‘democratic’ or not, might be a different matter, but I cannot enter this discussion here.) I therefore disregard this option and instead presuppose that agents engaged in extra-legal actions will also pursue the conservative-restorative purpose. Nevertheless, on the matter of constitutive power, see, for instance, O. CHESSA, *Sovranità, potere costituente, stato d’eccezione. Tre sfide per la teoria della norma di riconoscimento*, in *Diritto pubblico*, n. 3/2012; C. MORTATI, *La teoria del potere costituente*, Macerata, Quodlibet, 2020 [1945]; J. BAQUERIZO MINUCHE, *El concepto de ‘poder constituyente’. Un estudio de teoría analítica del Derecho*, Madrid, Marcial Pons, 2021.

First, that a response to an emergency is ‘law-based’, I take to mean, quite simply, that the relevant extraordinary measures are adopted on the basis – and within limits – of some legal norm¹¹. In fact, the ‘legality’ of emergency response is the salient feature that fundamentally distinguishes this from the other examined approach (i.e. the state of exception). On this latter approach, the response to an emergency is not based on any legal norm and altogether escapes the legal framework. The argument that emergencies ought to be confronted in such an extra-legal manner is actually quite common, both in literature and in practice. Echoing Schmitt¹², the argument states that the law is an instrument designed to regulate «the ordinary and the normal» which – given the unpredictability of emergency events and, thus, their radical concreteness – «cannot always provide for such extraordinary occurrences in spite of its aspiration to comprehensiveness»¹³. Already Locke argued that when rigid execution of the laws would be detrimental to the public good, the executive has ‘the prerogative’, i.e. the «power to act according to discretion for the public good, without the prescription of the law, and sometimes even against it»¹⁴. However, more recently, Postema has contrasted this view by arguing that «even when it may not be possible to precisely fix a *rule* in advance to fit a nonroutine situation, we often can identify broad features of situations and circumstances that will call for responses of certain recognizable kinds»¹⁵. Thus, Postema holds that though concrete rules may not be predisposed for guiding actions in emergencies, sufficiently identifiable features of these latter emerge regularly so as to allow for the identification of broad general types of responses to them.

Second, the activation of the state of emergency is neither the result of a normative automatism, by which I mean that whenever conditions are met, the emergency mechanism is triggered *ex lege*; nor of a purely arbitrary decision unconstrained by any formal or substantive criterion. Instead, it stems from a norm-based and rational decision-making process of public reason-giving, whereby the agent is called upon to determine and explain whether the instruments of the state of emergency are an appropriate, necessary and sufficient means for achieving the purpose pursued by the use of these instruments (so-

¹¹ This norm can either be at the legislative or the constitutional level of regulation. Here, I presuppose the existence of constitutional-level norms. This presupposition is corroborated by the fact that currently more than 90% of the world’s countries have some kind of emergency-related norms contained in their constitutions (see C. BJØRNSKOV – S. VOIGT, *The architecture of emergency constitutions*, in *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, n. 16(1)/2018, 101).

¹² In *Political Theology*, Schmitt famously argued that «[e]very general norm demands a normal, everyday frame of life to which it can be factually applied and which is subjected to its regulations ... There exists no norm that is applicable to chaos. For a legal order to make sense, a normal situation must exist ...» (C. SCHMITT, *Political Theology. Four Chapters on the Concept of Sovereignty* (1922), Chicago, University of Chicago Press, 2005, 13).

¹³ C. FATOVIC, *Outside the Law. Emergency and Executive Power*, cit., 2.

¹⁴ J. LOCKE, *Two Treatises of Government*, London, Everyman, 1993 (1689), 198 (par. 160). This claim allows us to further analytically distinguish between two forms of extra-legal action, namely *praeter legem* and *contra legem* action, respectively. In our context, while the former refers to actions in which the agent intentionally disapplies state of emergency norms, perhaps applying instead some alternative norms or no norm at all, the latter refers to actions that directly violate the relevant set of norms that regulate (constitutional) emergency management.

¹⁵ See G. POSTEMA, *Law’s Rule: The Nature, Value, and Viability of the Rule of Law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2022, 252.

called ‘judgment of necessity’¹⁶). On the other hand, the decision to act extra-legally is arbitrary in the sense that it is unbound by any pre-existing criteria contained in legal norms that govern emergency decision-making, and that it needn’t be rational¹⁷. As in the previous case, here too, the agent will inevitably be engaged in the judgment of necessity on the use of extraordinary powers. The difference, however, is that in this latter case, the agent’s answer as to the appropriateness, necessity and sufficiency of the legally-determined mechanisms will inevitably be radically opposite: namely, that it is necessary to adopt measures and procedures that are not constrained by legal norms¹⁸.

As these two models are articulated at the design level of constitutional theory, they clearly do not exhaust the analysis of emergency governance. On the contrary, they only provide the conceptual and normative framework within which concrete emergency responses are interpreted and enacted in practice. It is therefore appropriate at this time to turn to frontline emergency management and some of its salient characteristics.

4. The necessity of frontline discretion and the danger of arbitrariness

It is in the actual dealings of firefighters, paramedics, police officers and other frontline agents in specific emergency situations that theoretical emergency models and normative frameworks come to life. While the contents of these models and frameworks do matter for different reasons, they nevertheless are not self-executing and merely empower different emergency action without actually enforcing them. What is ultimately required for this are the concrete material actions of frontline agents. In this context, it is a fundamental characteristic of their decision-making that in adopting their actions they hold ample ‘operational discretion’. This space for autonomous decision-making is the salient characteristic that most profoundly defines the nature of the frontline agents’ activities and so it deserves further examination. As we will see, however, the very same characteristics of their working context that allow for this discretion also create the danger that the very same degenerates into extra-legal ‘arbitrariness’. Let us first have a closer look at the pertinent factors that contribute to the discretion of frontline emergency agents.

¹⁶ Cf. MARAZZITA, *L'emergenza costituzionale. Definizioni e modelli*, cit., 179 ff. (“il giudizio di necessità”). See also Rossiter, who states that constitutional dictatorship should not be instituted «*unless it is necessary or even indispensable to the preservation of the state and its constitutional order*» (C. ROSSITER, *Constitutional Dictatorship. Crisis Government in the Modern Democracies*, cit., 298; emphases mine).

¹⁷ Cf. T. ENDICOTT, *Arbitrariness*, in *Canadian Journal of Law & Jurisprudence*, n. 27(1)/2014 («Arbitrariness is a lack of reason.») Such arbitrariness, however, does not necessarily mean that there are absolutely no limits on the agent’s decision-making processes. For example, specific social and political conditions may constrain the agent to present her decision (if not her arguments) in a public forum, either *ex ante* or *ex post*.

¹⁸ As to the question of ‘who’ may act as the *de facto* decision-maker, the answer, in principle, is that anyone may assume the position of ‘the sovereign’ and adopt emergency-resolving decisions. This follows from Carl Schmitt’s famous – albeit terribly vague – definition of the sovereign as «*he who decides on the exception*» (C. SCHMITT, *Political Theology. Four Chapters on the Concept of Sovereignty*, cit., 5). However, in practice, the set of possible “exceptional agents” will be highly limited and will typically correspond to the set of those agents that would otherwise be legally authorized to act in a state of emergency – hence, primarily, the executive. Cf. B. BUZAN – O. WAEVER – J. DE WILDE, *Security: A New Framework for Analysis*, cit., 40 ff.

First of all, discretion is an inherently elusive concept, subject to a wide range of competing definitions. Yet, a shared core can be identified in two closely connected features: first, it entails a degree of freedom on the part of the decision-maker to select among alternative courses of action; second, this freedom is exercised within a framework that is structured and constrained by rules¹⁹.

Secondly, that there is always a necessary space for discretion in the implementation of normative acts is something we may apprehend starting from purely theoretical considerations. For instance, we know from Merkel-Kelsen's *Stufenbaulehre* theory that legal systems are organized in a hierarchical structure of norms and acts in which higher-level norms (or acts) authorize and frame the creation of lower-level norms (or acts)²⁰. Higher-level norms determine the procedures according to which lower-level norms ought to be created (or the act of execution performed) and can also determine the contents of those norms (or act). However, what is here crucial for our purposes, Kelsen argues that «[t]his determination can never be complete. The higher norm cannot bind in every direction the act by which it is applied. There must always be more or less room for *discretion*, so that the higher norm in relation to the lower one can only have the character of a frame to be filled by this act»²¹. In other terms, higher-level norms can only partially predetermine the contents of lower-level norms or executive acts. As Kelsen underlines, this inevitably means that there is a certain structural margin of discretion that agents have in the act of implementation. Note that such discretion can either be the intentional result of purposefully indeterminate norms or it can be «the unintended result of the way in which the legal norm is formulated that is to be applied by the act in question»²². In any case, such 'normative vagueness' allows the acting agents ample (interpretative) discretion in applying norms to concrete cases²³.

There are, however, also other sources of frontline discretion, outside of the structural characteristics of the normative order itself. These, on the contrary, are related to the ontological characteristics of emergencies themselves. For instance, the 'unpredictability of emergency situations' makes it the case that the greater the complexity of a given situation, the greater the need for discretionary judgment. Indeed, where events lack significant complexity or novelty and are amenable to established routines, frontline officials are more likely – and better positioned – to adhere to prescribed procedures and hierarchical

¹⁹ For more, see, for instance, K.C. DAVIS, *Discretionary Justice A Preliminary Inquiry*, Baton Rouge, Louisiana State University Press, 1969; R. DWORKIN, *Taking Rights Seriously*, Cambridge (Mass.), Harvard University Press, 1977, 31 ss.; T. ENDICOTT, *Administrative law*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2011, 234 ss.; M. LIPSKY, *Street-Level Bureaucracy: Dilemmas of the Individual in Public Services*, New York, Russell Sage Foundation, 30th anniversary expanded ed., 2010, 13 ss.

²⁰ H. KELSEN, *Pure Theory of Law*, Clark (N.J.), The Lawbook Exchange, 2005, 221 f.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 349 (emphasis mine).

²² *Ibid.*, 349-350. Also, on implicit and explicit delegation of law-making powers to administrative bodies, see H. S. RICHARDSON, *Administrative Policy-making: Rule of Law or Bureaucracy?*, in D. DYZENHAUS (a cura di), *Recrafting the Rule of Law: The Limits of Legal Order*, Portland (Or.), Hart Publishing, 1999, 311.

²³ Take, for example, Article 92 of the Slovenian Constitution which determines that a state of emergency can be declared when a "great and general danger" threatens the "existence" of the state. The exact meaning of these terms is highly vague and invites discretionary interpretation.

directives. On the other hand, in complex situations that present original features unaligned with protocols and other *ex ante* rules and procedures, greater improvisation is required from frontline agents. Additionally, situational complexity also increases the difficulty of overseeing and monitoring the frontline agents' actions on the grounds which, again, increases the space for autonomous decision-making²⁴. Moreover, the 'dangerousness' of emergencies, and their potentially rapid development, provokes the necessity to decide urgently. This rootedness of emergencies in the present moment makes them ill-suited for governance through statutes and other slow and rigid normative mechanisms that require much time for analysis, reconsideration and implementation. Instead, flexible, "just-in-time" decision-making is required²⁵. Additionally, the fact that frontline agents possess 'superior professional and situational knowledge'²⁶, increases the likelihood – given the already mentioned unpredictability of emergencies and the decision-making urgency – that they will deviate from top-down directions and protocols and, instead, act on the basis of their own judgment, especially when they assess that these directions and protocols do not fit the *in situ* conditions²⁷.

The ample operational discretion of frontline agents has another important source as it stems from the distinctiveness of their 'organizational position'. On the one hand, these agents represent the very last rung in an institution's hierarchical chain of command. As the final link, they are expected to adhere to the set of relevant norms and carry out their superiors' orders. On the other hand, however, they are the only agents of a particular institution who actually perform their work in direct contact with individuals and often – as in our case – in an environment that is physically detached from the institutional halls. This latter peculiarity of their working condition, in particular, affords frontline agents ample decision-making discretion. As Lipsky confirms, «certain characteristics of the jobs of street-level bureaucrats make it difficult, if not impossible, to severely reduce discretion»²⁸. This is so, because, first, they work in situations that are too complicated to be reduced to "programmatically formats". Second, because they work «in situations that often require responses to the human dimensions of situations»²⁹. Hence, professional discretion is a not an exception, but a structural feature of the frontline (emergency) agents' position

²⁴ M. MEYERS – V. LEHMANN NIELSEN, *Street-level Bureaucrats and the Implementation of Public Policy*, in B. GUY PETERS – J. PIERRE (a cura di), *The SAGE Handbook of Public Administration*, London, SAGE, 2012, 308; J.P. KALKMAN, *Frontline Workers in Crisis Management*, in *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Crisis Analysis* (online version), 2020.

²⁵ I. GJERGJI, *Immigrazione e infra-diritto: dal governo per circolari alla tweeting governance*, in *Etica & Politica*, n. XXII, 2020; M. ZGUR, *Infra-law in frontline emergency decision-making: mediating discretion and rule-following*, in *Materiali per una storia della cultura giuridica*, n. 1, 2026.

²⁶ J.P. KALKMAN, *Frontline Workers in Crisis Management*, cit.

²⁷ This is particularly true of agents working within goal-oriented professional cultures. Van Scotter and Leonard, for instance, report that paramedics are «socialized to think and act independently and often challenge authority». They go on to say that «[t]he judgment of authorities within paramedical organizations is frequently overruled by lower ranking members on the scene with superior knowledge of the patient's condition, medical science, or best practices in medical care» (J. VAN SCOTTER – K. MOUSTAFA LEONARD, *Clashes of cultures during crises: coordinating firefighters, police and paramedic interactions*, in *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, n. 31(4)/2022, 379).

²⁸ M. LIPSKY, *Street-Level Bureaucracy: Dilemmas of the Individual in Public Services*, cit., 15. Lipsky defines street-level bureaucrats as «[p]ublic service workers who interact directly with citizens in the course of their jobs, and who have substantial discretion in the execution of their work» (*Ibid.*, 3).

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 15.

in their specific working environment. It follows that while frontline officials are formally subordinate to their superiors (and the whole hierarchical organizational pyramid above them), they are nevertheless structurally very much autonomous in their work-related choices.

However, this ample operational discretion, as useful and necessary as it may be, at the same time also contains the possibility of frontline agents taking undue advantage of their operational autonomy and ‘abusing’ their powers. This can be done either by overstepping or contradicting the normative framework determining legitimate emergency actions or even by directly disregarding or disobeying the operational directives of superiors. Importantly, such deviations can either come in the form of isolated or sporadic occurrences, or they can be systemic. The slippage into extra-legal arbitrariness that I have in mind here should not be understood as single acts of illegality, not even an unconnected occasional set of them, but rather as a gradual transformation in the operative logic of frontline decision-making. This occurs when repeated discretionary deviations, initially justified as context-specific responses, become stabilized, generalized and decoupled from the justificatory framework of the law. At that point, the legal regime that formally remains in place becomes functionally displaced by a practice governed by an extra-legal, necessity-oriented reasoning.

We see that a thin and slippery line separates the legitimate exercise of the necessary operational discretion from arbitrary abuse of extraordinary emergency powers³⁰. Crucially, illegality in the form of arbitrary frontline decision-making does not require constitutional suspension. Instead, as we have just seen, it can emerge even from legitimate discretion which is a structural feature of any legal regime, including, and especially, of those under emergency accommodation. In these latter cases, this possibility is even more problematic considering that adherence to legality is fundamental precisely in those moments when the resilience of the legal and political institutions of a community are tested by crisis events. (II) Legality of emergency action crystallizes at the moment of frontline implementation. It is the standing possibility of frontline professional discretion devolving into extra-legal arbitrariness that risks undermining the legitimacy of the legal framework of the accommodation model (the state of emergency). If frontline agents are empowered to ignore, modify or contradict superior law and directives, there exists the danger that emergency responses will, in general, become too detached from legal standards and democratic oversight, which are vital for maintaining legality in times of crisis.

Thus, if professional discretion is structurally inevitable; if legality is only fully affirmed at the frontlines; and if slippage into arbitrariness is a standing possibility in frontline emergency management ..., then the decisive question is not whether emergencies can and should be governed legally or extra-legally in the abstract, at the level of theoretical models or constitutional frameworks. Instead, we should look at how – and why – frontline emergency agents act in concrete emergency situations, how they comprehend their roles

³⁰ On arbitrariness, defined as a «departure from the rule of law, in favor of rule by the mere will of the rulers», see T. ENDICOTT, *Arbitrariness*, cit., 49.

– including their decision-making authority – and how they perceive the relevance of maintaining legality under conditions of stress. Moreover, and more specifically, we need to understand why the exercise of frontline discretion sometimes remains within legality-preserving confines and sometimes deteriorates into legality-eroding activities.

5. A matter of professional (legal) culture

In our initial example (above, 1.), we saw that radically different approaches to frontline emergency management are possible even in reference to the same emergency situation governed by the same normative framework. It is true, on the one hand, that theoretical frameworks, constitutional norms or emergency decrees do not fully predetermine the set of possible actions regarding a given emergency. This, however, does not mean that slippage into extra-legal arbitrariness is inevitable. Frontline emergency management is not a free-for-all. In other words, we must reject both the idea of “implementation automatism” – whereby legal norms would somehow be mechanically implemented to the letter without any autonomous deliberation on the part of frontline agents; as well as the idea of “decisionist fatalism” – whereby emergency decision-making would by necessity be unhinged and arbitrary, regardless of pre-existing rules and procedures. Beyond these two unrealistic extremes, the decision-making space at the frontlines allows for a variety of different emergency management approaches within legal confines.

But if neither the normative sources framing frontline decision-making nor the phenomenology of emergencies can themselves ultimately fix the character of emergency agents’ responses, then what does? What motivates frontline emergency agents to adopt either a wider or a narrower interpretation of relevant norms and situational factors? What drives them to opt either for a more moderated, legally-bound approach or a more extreme, legally-unbound one? What are the salient factors that most profoundly influence the nature of emergency management actions on the frontlines? In this section, I seek to show – and, in so doing, confirm my initial claim (above, 2.) – that a crucial element in the way frontline agents exercise their emergency powers is constituted by the type of professional (legal) culture embodied by them.

First of all, by “professional (legal) culture” I mean the set of work-related dispositions, habits, normative expectations, deontological orientations, shared interpretive frameworks, and informal understandings through which frontline emergency agents relate to legal norms and superior directives, to peer and organizational dynamics, to the institutional constraints and accountability structures, and that jointly shape – at least in part – the nature of their emergency decision-making practices³¹. These dispositions, habits, expectations etc. are acquired at different stages of professional development and via different channels.

³¹ Cf. Schein, who defines organizational culture as «the set of shared, taken-for-granted implicit assumptions that a group holds and that determines how it perceives, thinks about, and reacts to its various environments» (E. SCHEIN, *Culture: The Missing Concept in Organizational Studies*, in *Administrative Science Quarterly*, n. 41(2)/1996, 236). The notion «refers to a shared value system that develops over time that guides team members as they experience and solve

While some argue that the nature of individuals' decision-making practices is mostly influenced by pre- and extra-organizational influences, namely the beliefs and past experiences that one brings into the workplace (the 'dispositional' perspective), others hold that it is primarily shaped by one's intra-organizational experiences (the 'institutional' perspective)³². Realistically, it must be correct to assume that the actual behavior of individuals is the result of an intricate combination of all of these types of influences. Despite this, here, I focus exclusively on the role of 'institutional' influences. This is because frontline discretion never operates in an institutional vacuum. It is always structured, enabled and constrained by the normative and organizational architecture within which it is exercised. The normative and organizational frameworks, therefore, define the range of legitimate actions, shape accountability mechanisms, and influence how discretion is distributed. Hence, it should be pointed out that professional (legal) culture does not replace institutional design, but rather mediates its practical effects.

Within this institutional perspective, according to which there is a fundamental expectation that «entrants will adopt new views as a result of contact with the social forces inside their organizations»³³, two broad views co-exist as to the main source of these influences: namely, the rational systems perspective and the natural systems perspective. On the 'rational systems' approach, organizations uniformly pursue a distinct goal and situate individuals within clearly-defined hierarchical structures in ways that shape their tasks, procedures, goals, accountability mechanisms etc., by way of formalizing the entirety of their institutional experiences. In so doing, organizations convey fundamental information to the recruits about how they are expected to think and behave, while also signaling the organization's core values³⁴. The success of these formal kinds of influence hinges primarily on the organization's capacity to instill in the individuals the acquisition of a disposition to (more or less) automatically follow selected behavioral patterns that correspond to the rules that guide their behavior³⁵. The foremost organizational mechanism for achieving this goal is formal training³⁶.

On the other hand, on the 'natural systems' approach, organizations are seen as more open to external influences and as places that tend to pursue multiple goals. On this view, the organization's formal instruments of influence are considered as less important for shaping behavior than its informal influences, such as informal norms, sub-cultures and peer interactions. Although outside of formal organizational schemes, these influences nevertheless crucially «orient organization members to what is appropriate behavior and ...

problems, adapt to their internal and external environments, and engage and manage relationships» (J. PERSON – L. SPIVA – P. HART, *The culture of an emergency department: An ethnographic study*, in *International Emergency Nursing*, n. 21/2013, 222).

³² Cf. Z. OBERFIELD, *Becoming Bureaucrats: Socialisation at the Front Lines of Government Service*, Philadelphia, University of Pennsylvania Press, 2014, 2.

³³ *Ibid.*, 31.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, 32.

³⁵ Cf. M. BRIGAGLIA, *Potere. Una rilettura di Michel Foucault*, Napoli, Editoriale Scientifica, 2019, 327.

³⁶ Cf. also H. SIMON, *Administrative Behavior: A Study of Decision-Making Processes in Administrative Organization* (4th ed.), New York, The Free Press, 1997, 9 and 13. On the role of training, see also BRIGAGLIA, *Potere. Una rilettura di Michel Foucault*, cit., 240-243.

establish perspectives about how they should think and act»³⁷. Again, here too, we should not fall into the trap of interpreting agents' behavior as exclusively the result of only one of these two types of influence – instead, their actual behavior is undoubtedly the result of a specific cohabitation of both types of formal and informal influences.

This is evidenced also by empirical studies into the different models of professional culture that develop among the members of different emergency services. For example, in a comparative examination of frontline emergency services cultures – namely, police, ambulance service and firefighters' cultures –, Wankhade and Patnaik concluded that all three services share a traditional, hierarchical, and strongly bound occupational identity³⁸. In addition, each service's culture is shaped by rank-based or authoritative structures and a masculine ethos, which reinforces group loyalty and solidarity. They are also characterized by close-knit workforce, operating in intense, high-risk environments, where shared experiences strengthen cohesion. The same authors highlight the historically entrenched, disciplined and group-oriented cultures with structural features that reinforce solidarity but also perpetuate problematic behaviours or resistance to change.

Similarly, in their study of police academy socialization, Chappell and Lanza-Kaduce argue that police academy training and organizations have a predominantly paramilitary-bureaucratic structure³⁹. This includes traditional bureaucratic features, such as a clear command hierarchy, an explicit rule system, complex division of labour etc. Moreover, they also partake of other military organization characteristics such as intense training, boot camp rituals, group punishments and discipline. As to the effects of such training and organizational features, these authors stress that «[s]uch socialization experiences are known to strip individuals of their personal characteristics so that they can embrace the 'esprit de corps' of the organization»⁴⁰. Thus, while the more formal, hierarchical, rational approach to organization and leadership is present in these organizations, recent years have, nevertheless, been characterized by a gradual shift towards more democratic and decentralized styles of police training and operation (so-called “community policing”). Hence, reformed curricula are being increasingly implemented across police academies and new types of recruits are also entering the force, although scholars acknowledge that much time will likely have to pass before these reforms are thoroughly implemented and their results visible on the frontlines.

While there are numerous different theories and cultural models on the marketplace of ideas and in operational practice, it seems we may, by-and-large, bundle them into two (Weberian) ideal-type models. For simplicity, I will call them the “authoritarian” model and the “democratic” model, respectively. On the first model, emergency services are characterized by an authoritarian, top-down, hierarchical command-and-control operation

³⁷ Z. OBERFIELD, *Becoming Bureaucrats: Socialisation at the Front Lines of Government Service*, cit., 33.

³⁸ P. WANKHADE – S. PATNAIK, *Collaboration and Governance in the Emergency Services. Issues, Opportunities and Challenges*, Cham, Palgrave MacMillan 2020: 109 ff.

³⁹ A. CHAPPELL – L. LANZA-KADUCE, *Police Academy Socialization: Understanding the Lessons Learned in a Paramilitary-Bureaucratic Organization*, in *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, n. 39(2)/2010.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*, 189.

type, promote explicit rule systems, establish complex division of labor, and exhibit high masculinity and traditionalism, resistance to change and other similar cultural characteristics⁴¹. On the other hand, more recent times have been characterized by increasing reforms of the training and organizational regimes within emergency services, in particular police forces. This other – democratic – model, thus, promotes a more horizontal communication culture, organizational decentralization, enhanced officials' accountability, interactive training, soft skills etc.

The key question at this point is how do the behaviors typically attributable to these two models relate to the question of the legality of frontline emergency governance? More specifically, how do cultural patterns, typical of these two models, mediate between frontline discretion and normative constraints to produce the actual frontline behavior? (Before we try to answer this question, it should be noted that the two models are here treated merely as ideal-type constructs that represent two unrealistic extreme positions. In practice, we may reasonably assume that the actual organizational cultural models will be hybrid.)

On the thesis I am advancing here, the legality of frontline emergency governance hinges, in an important way, on the way frontline agents are socialized in understanding their roles in relation to operational discretion, on the one hand, and the value of normative and institutional frameworks, on the other hand. Their actions are filtered through their individual and shared understanding of what is considered appropriate behavior both inter- and intra-organizationally, what operational goals ought to be prioritized, how citizens' rights constrain possible actions etc. Clearly, the two ideal models presented above provide two different responses on this matter.

Where emergency agents are predominantly exposed to authoritarian (even militarized) socialization, all activities, including the use of discretion, tend to be oriented towards efficient mission accomplishment. On this approach, substantive legal norms and procedural safeguards are not necessarily outright rejected – indeed, they can sometimes be rigorously followed, but they are often perceived as defeasible outside constraints that may have to yield to other values, principles and decision-making criteria, if they appear to obstruct operational success in any way. The interpretative space left open by indeterminate norms and discretion-favoring situational features is likely to be filled expansively. Thus, for example, broadly-worded decrees are viewed as mandates to do “whatever is necessary” to achieve the operational goals. Importantly, on this approach, the formal normative framework of the state of emergency needn't be changed, yet the actions of frontline officials may very well constitute *de facto* extra-legal actions from time to time.

By contrast, in a cultural milieu shaped by democratic and legality-oriented commitments, discretion is understood more as a responsibility. On this approach, emergency powers are considered as legally-framed competencies whose purpose is not only to allow for the situation to be efficiently resolved, but also to preserve and restore the

⁴¹ Cf. P. WANKHADE – S. PATNAIK, *Collaboration and Governance in the Emergency Services. Issues, Opportunities and Challenges*, cit., 109.

status quo of the normative order in so doing. The key question driving operational activities shifts: the issue is not just how to stop the emergency as quickly as possible, but how to do so within the confines of the conferred mandate. Here, issues such as proportionality, consultation with superiors and with local communities, sensitivity to individual rights etc. are not so much seen as impediments to efficient action but rather as key elements that constitute a legitimate emergency response. While emergency action within an accommodation model is still flexible and context-sensitive it is nevertheless anchored in a strong culturally-conditioned commitment to legality.

6. Conclusion

Emergency theory has long been preoccupied with the architecture of exceptional powers: who may declare them, under what conditions, and subject to which formal constraints. These questions remain indispensable. Yet the argument developed in this article suggests that they are incomplete. As has been shown in this paper, the decisive arena in which the legality of emergency governance is ultimately settled is not exhausted by constitutional text, judicial doctrine, or institutional design. It is found, rather, at the emergency frontlines. We saw this in our initial example (1.): while the first group of frontline officials treated the emergency-related normative framework as a bounded authorization requiring individualized assessment, self-restraint and a rights-oriented focus, the second group treated it more as a broad mandate for coercive intervention, subordinating procedural safeguards to operational needs and a narrow goal-focused mission.

The original distinction made between the state of emergency and the state of exception is a design-level one. One model aspires for emergency actions to remain within the law; the other allows for implicit or open departures from it. But the above analysis demonstrates that this boundary is not secured once and for all by constitutional drafting. It is continuously renegotiated through discretionary practices of frontline agents. For example, a formally declared state of emergency can, through expansive interpretations and culturally conditioned “mission-first” reasoning, slide into a *de facto* state of exception. Conversely, even under conditions of urgency, uncertainty and danger, a rights-oriented and self-restraining professional culture can sustain legality as an actual practice rather than a merely textual commitment.

These insights carry several theoretical implications. First, discretion is not an anomaly of emergency governance but its structural condition. Because higher-level norms can never fully determine their application, and because emergencies are complex, time-sensitive and situationally volatile, frontline agents inevitably operate within a discretionary space. The central question, therefore, is not whether discretion can be eliminated – as it clearly cannot be – but how can it be oriented. Discretion may be harnessed by commitment to legality, or it may function as a conduit for arbitrariness.

Second, and following from the former point, not every instance of illegality in the form of abuse of discretion should be interpreted as already a manifestation of an exceptional logic. Isolated or sporadic violations can well be said to be tolerable internal deviations within a fundamentally legal normative framework. By contrast, when such practices become sufficiently stable, generalized and normatively reoriented, in a way that they are no longer justified by reference to some constitutional framework but instead by exclusively necessity-oriented reasoning, then they can be said to have acquired an exceptionalist character. In such cases, we may argue that an alternative, extra-legal logic of action has emerged that functionally displaces law-compliant behavior.

Third, professional (legal) culture emerges as a constitutive element of emergency legality. Training regimes, internal accountability structures, peer expectations, leadership narratives, and organizational self-understandings shape how agents perceive their operational mandate. Whether legality is treated as an internal constraint, a defeasible obstacle, or an integral part of mission success depends on these cultural formations. In this sense, legality in emergencies is not secured solely by institutional design, but also by the agents' institutional character.

Fourth, our analysis complicates the familiar opposition between legality and effectiveness. In authoritarian organizational cultures, legality may be framed as a secondary consideration, i.e. as something to be respected insofar as it does not obstruct operational success. In more legality-oriented cultures, by contrast, adherence to proportionality, documentation, consultation and fundamental rights of citizens is integrated as criteria into the very meaning of effective emergency response. The divergence between legality-preserving and legality-eroding practices is therefore not reducible to the intensity of the crisis or the wording of the normative sources, but also depends on how agents are socialized to understand their roles.

If this is correct, the resilience of emergency legality depends on more than the sophistication of theoretical models or the semantic precision of constitutional drafting. It depends equally, if not more so, on investments in professional socialization – on embedding Rule of Law commitments into training and promotion criteria, on cultivating leadership styles that frame legality as a non-negotiable dimension of professional excellence, and so forth. The maintenance of constitutional democracy in times of crisis thus requires attention not only to constitutional safeguards, but also to the frontline institutions through which power is exercised in practice. Ultimately, emergencies test not only legal systems but legal cultures as well. Normative frameworks provide the grammar of emergency governance, but frontline agents are the ones who make it work. Whether they remain within the bounds of law or drift into the sphere of the extra-legal exception is determined, in no small part, by the professional habitus in which emergency agents are trained and in which they operate.